

FLUOBERYLLATES AND THEIR ANALOGY WITH SULPHATES. PART VII.
COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF FLUOBERYLLATES WITH HEXAMETHYLENE-
TETRAMINE, PYRIDINE AND QUINOLINE

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Complex compounds of fluoberyllates of nickel, copper, cobalt and zinc with hexamethylenetetramine, pyridine and quinoline have been prepared. These complex fluoberyllates are analogous to the corresponding complex sulphates. This investigation adds further proof of the analogy of fluoberyllates to sulphates.

In continuation of the previous work on the fluoberyllates and their ammoniacal complex in which analogy between the fluoberyllates and sulphates has been established (Ray, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, 241, 165), it has now been observed that, like the sulphates, the fluoberyllates of bivalent metals, e.g. nickel, copper, zinc and cobalt, also form well defined compounds with hexamethylenetetramine, pyridine and quinoline.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hexamethylenetetramine Compounds

Hexamethylenetetramine-nickel fluoberyllate.—On adding a saturated solution of nickel fluoberyllate to a saturated aqueous solution of hexamethylenetetramine at ordinary temperature and shaking, the colour of the solution faded, heat was evolved and shining pale green crystals appeared. The crystals were washed with 80% alcohol and dried in air. (Found : Ni, 13.95 ; Be, 2.31 ; N, 13.88. $\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 14.31 ; Be, 2.20 ; N 13.67 per cent).

These pale green crystals are stable and soluble in water. When dried at 120°—125° it lost all its water. (Found : N, 19.38. Calc. for the anhydrous compound : N, 19.73 per cent). The anhydrous salt is yellowish green.

Hexamethylenetetramine-cobalt fluoberyllate was prepared like the corresponding nickel compounds. It forms pink coloured crystals. (Found : Co, 14.06 ; Be, 2.18 ; N, 13.56. $\text{CoBeF}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 14.36 ; Be, 2.20 ; N, 13.65 per cent).

It lost all its water at 120°—125°. (Found : N, 19.51. Calc. for the anhydrous compound : N, 19.71 per cent).

Pyridine Complexes

2 NiBeF_4 . 9 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ was prepared by digesting finely powdered and dehydrated nickel fluoberyllate with pyridine on the water-bath at 80° for about 2 hours. The product was filtered through a dry filter paper, and dried by pressing between folds of filter papers and then in air. (Found : Ni, 11.47 ; Be, 1.89. 2 NiBeF_4 . 9 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Ni, 11.74 ; Be, 1.81 per cent).

It slowly gives off pyridine in air and is decomposed by water.

The above compound, when triturated with absolute alcohol and washed several times with the same solvent and dried as usual, was converted into 2 NiBeF_4 . 5 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$. This resembles the parent substance in properties. (Found : Ni, 16.62 ; Be, 2.57. 2 NiBeF_4 . 5 $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Ni, 17.19 ; Be, 2.64 per cent).

The pyridine complex of the corresponding sulphates are also very unstable.

Tetra-pyridine-copper fluoberyllate was prepared in the same way as the nickel compound described before. (Found : Cu, 13.59 ; Be, 1.95. $\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Cu, 13.66 ; Be, 1.94 per cent). It forms a blue unstable crystalline product.

Dipyridine-copper fluoberyllate dihydrate was prepared by adding dropwise a saturated solution of copper fluoberyllate to pyridine on a water-bath and shaking for 15 to 20 minutes. This was kept in a frigidaire until crystallised. The crystals were filtered, washed with acetone and dried in air. (Found : Cu, 18.66 ; Be, 2.53. $\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 19.00 ; Be 2.71 per cent).

An analogous compound with copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been described by Chang and Hū (*J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 10, 113).

Quinoline Complexes

Monoquinoline-nickel fluoberyllate was prepared in the same way as described for the preceding compound. Quinoline was estimated by dissolving a weighed quantity of the compound in excess of *N/10-HCl* and the excess of the acid was titrated with *N/10-NaOH* solution (cf. Bhattacharjee and Sinha, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 21). (Found : Ni, 21.64 ; Be, 3.10. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$, 46.76. $\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ requires Ni, 21.50 ; Be, 3.30 ; $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$, 47.32 per cent). The compound is fairly stable in air and liberates quinoline slowly.

Quinoline-dicopper fluoberyllate was prepared in the same way as described in the copper-pyridine complex using quinoline in place of pyridine. (Found : Cu, 30.6 ; Be, 4.19. $2\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ requires Cu, 29.81 ; Be, 4.23 per cent). This compound is stable in air. Chang and Yü (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, 243, 14) obtained a corresponding compound with copper sulphate.

Triquinoline-copper fluoberyllate was prepared as above by adding quinoline dropwise to a copper fluoberyllate solution at 0°. (Found : Cu, 11.60 ; Be, 1.62. $\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 3\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ requires Cu, 11.85 ; Be, 1.68 per cent). This compound is, however, not so stable.

Quinoline-zinc fluoberyllate tetrahydrate was prepared in the same way as that used for quinoline di-copper fluoberyllate. (Found : Zn, 18.39 ; Be, 2.57. $\text{ZnBeF}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 18.59 ; Be, 2.57 per cent). This is fairly stable in air.